

DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S CREATIVE THINKING BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article describes the components of integration, the integration approach and the advantages of the integration approach in developing the creative thinking of primary school students.*

Keywords: *education, student, upbringing, creativity, creative thinking, integration, integrative approach.*

It is no secret to any of us that in today's era of globalization, the issue of educating students as mature individuals, competent and competitive personnel remain relevant. In the implementation of this process, the need to form and grow the creative thinking of students in the primary education system is emphasized. The process of thinking has been interesting to people since ancient times. Even ancient philosophers thought about its role in human life. Because the philosopher and physicist Albert Einstein said about thinking that "thought is stronger than knowledge"

According to the "Dictionary of Pedagogical Terms" compiled under the leadership of Professor R.Kh. Jorayev, thinking is the highest form of human mental activity, the process of reflection of objective existence in the mind. In modern psychology, thinking is described as "the process of cognitive activity of a person, a generalized and indirect reflection of reality; the highest form of creative activity"

Educational Integration is a high level of interdisciplinary communication, a tool that allows creating a whole integrated knowledge. The definitions given to the concept of integration are different, the general aspect of these definitions is that integration consists in achieving a holistic view of the existence around us.

The basis of integration is interdisciplinarity and finds its development in the idea of integration. Studying subjects with an integrative content is considered as a factor that ensures the knowledge, working methods, and personal qualities of future specialists.

According to Yu.M. Kolyagin, integration in the education system can be used in two different ways:

1. Forming a whole, integrated vision of the world around us in students (where integration is considered as an educational goal).
2. Finding a common platform for converging the knowledge provided by subjects (here it is an integration-educational tool).

Integration according to the first meaning, as soon as the student takes the first step in the field of knowledge, imagine the world as a whole, as a whole, all its elements are interconnected.

In the second sense, integration should be able to realize new ideas at the point of mutual collision of knowledge from academic subjects. At the beginning, at the point of collision of ideas

in the sciences, let him call to fill the gaps in the existing stratified knowledge, to find the connections between them.

We found it necessary to express integration in education as follows:

1. Forming a holistic image of the whole being is considered here as the goal of integration education;

2. Finding a common platform to bring different scientific knowledge closer together

3. As a means of developing education.

4. As a means of universal, national education.

In the establishment of connections between two educational subjects and their integration, one or another subject serves as a basis from time to time. The basis of integrated lessons should be the organic connection and logical interrelationship of topics in different academic subjects.

Components of integration. It became clear from the conducted research that integration has certain components. This is what is discussed below.

Object-related integration: in this, representations of the same object from different disciplines are included in the same subject, department or courses (earth, water, air, food, etc.).

Conceptual integration: This involves covering a topic or course that exposes the content of common concepts.

Integration of theory: it is quantum theory in physics, chemistry, biology; based on evolutionary theory in biology, chemistry, astronomy, technology, sociology.

Methodological integration: integration related to separate methods of scientific knowledge, such as the methodology of philosophy, the application of a systematic approach to them and its essence, the setting of problems related to natural science and their solution, explanation and forecasting in science; observation, experience, structure essence and application of modeling are included.

Problematic integration: covers interdisciplinary problems of different breadth (environmental protection, anti-drugs, etc.).

Activity integration: discussion, group work, interdisciplinary planning and project creation, etc.

Practical integration: a comprehensive review of various process or technical products, antibiotics, synthetics, biotechnology, computers, etc.

In today's educational process, it is no longer enough to provide students with knowledge of a certain system and demand that they memorize it. As a reason for this, we can cite the increasing demand in the labor market and society for personnel who are not only educated, but also have a broad outlook and creative thinking. In order to train such personnel, it is necessary to increase students' aspirations for independent education, to stimulate their interest in learning, and to promote integrated education more broadly.

An integrative approach prioritizes learning across the curriculum, emphasizes the connection of concepts and experiences, and allows the application of acquired knowledge and skills to new and complex problems that may be encountered. . An integrated curriculum focuses on making meaningful connections between subjects and skills that span multiple areas of learning, leading to a more enriched learning experience. Emphasizing the inevitability of deep integration processes in modern education, I.E. Kashekova writes: "The modern world is built on an integrated basis, it requires multifaceted knowledge, skills, the ability to choose the right information from

the flow of information and manage it competently; education should also be built on an integrative basis, introduce a person to a new world and help to master it.

The integrated educational space of the school eliminates the need to repeat the educational material and provides systematic and integrated knowledge about the world, human culture, and their components. As in life, students are given interdisciplinary tasks that stimulate the integration of knowledge in different disciplines, in the process of solving these problems, they search for information, translate scientific messages from one language to another.

Features of integrated education:

- Encourages professors and teachers to be more creative and inquisitive in the development of educational programs:

- Teaches how to check and use information effectively;
- Allows children to combine ideas and experiences to create new learning situations;
- Includes creativity, flexibility, critical thinking and collaboration;
- Covers a variety of learning styles, theories and practice.

As a result of observing and analyzing the data, we came to the following conclusions, the formation of creative thinking of students is the need of the hour. Primary school teachers have a big role in this process. They need to identify and constantly develop the creative thinking skills of their students, teach them to analyze and compare. Also, they are responsible for encouraging students' creative abilities and creating a friendly atmosphere, making creative thinking a habit. Creativity does not become a habit among students who are afraid of making mistakes, afraid of success, paying attention to excessive grades, and fearing criticism. In the rapidly developing global world, the teacher must be constantly in search, be active in the field of education with new ideas and thoughts. The use of interdisciplinary integration is of particular importance in teaching students to be creative and to be able to freely get out of various situations that they may encounter in life. Although the integrated approach to subjects requires more time from the teacher in the process of preparing lessons, it will show its positive result in the future.

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